

MANAGING THE IMPLICATIONS OF FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGY ON THE ASSETS OF INSURANCE COMPANIES IN NIGERIA. 2000-2022.

**¹Ezema, Clifford Anene. (Ph.D.), ²Nwankwo, Bobby- Godwin Ogbogu
(Ph.D.) and ³Ikechukwu Obeleagu Jeff**

^{1,3}Department of Insurance and Risk Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, (ESUT), Enugu state, Nigeria.

²Department of Accountancy, Faculty of Management Sciences Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu

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Abstract:

The insurance industry has always been a complicated but firmly rooted business environment, but advancements in technology have collided with customer needs, creating systemic challenges for the insurance industry. Mobile players in the industry saw these challenges and introduced customer value with mobile solutions. Compelled by the success of financial technology cum and Insurance technology maxims. Financial technology seem to improve insurance technology and as well as economy. The broad objective of the study is to examine the implications of financial technology on the assets of insurance company in Nigeria. The followings are the specific objectives of the study; investigate the implications of mobile pay on the assets of the insurance company. Determine the implications of A.T.M. on the assets of insurance company. Measure the implications national electronic transfer on the assets of the insurance company. Ordinary least square regression model was used in the analysis. This study examined the implications of financial technology on the assets of insurance company in Nigeria, using annual time series data from 2009 – 2022. From the analysis carried out, the following findings were postulated. Automated Teller Machine (ATM) had Positive and non-significant impact on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. Mobile pay had no positive and non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) had negative and non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria.

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From the empirical result, it shows that financial technology proxies which include Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Mobile Pay and National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) has non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. From the findings, Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has negative and non-significant effect on return on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. Mobile pay has no positive and non-significant effect on return on asset of commercial banks in Nigeria National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) has positive and non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. Therefore the study concludes that financial technology (Fintech) had positive and non-significant impact on the assets of insurance industry in Nigeria within the period under review.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The insurance industry has always been a complicated but firmly rooted environment, but advancements in technology have collided with customer needs, creating systemic challenges for the insurance industry. Mobile players in the industry saw these challenges and introduced customer value with mobile solutions. Compelled by the success of FinTech and InsurTech startups, the insurance industry is experiencing a systematic change in business operations (Abata, 2020). InsurTechs have many advantages that insurance companies can and should leverage. These startups are free from legacy products and processes, and they can use emerging technologies to build brand new systems. As a result, they can target specific value pools instead of offering lengthy end-to-end solutions that don't meet everyone's needs (Cihak & Singh, 2019).

Simon -Taylor, the founder of Get Indemnity in 1987, explains how Fintech has helped to overhaul financial services, by digitizing key processes. This includes the proposition of online application forms, online customer portals to upload policies and documentation, Omni channel support to request feedback from customers and offering our services across mobile and apps, he says. Taylor considers that the insurance market will follow in the footsteps of the banking industry and allow for better integrations through APIs. Insurer's legacy systems remain an obstacle, but the ability to capture and transfer detailed risk information creates efficiencies and provides underwriters with better data to price individual risks (Deloitte, 2018). Getting young people to purchase your insurance product is so important for business because they could renew each year and for the foreseeable future. But with Fintech today, insurers can offer far better premiums and

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products for young people - and not automatically overcharge them based on just their age, but taking thousands of characteristics into consideration (Diyan & Basuki, 2021).

Insurance business in any economy is deemed essential to economic growth. Indeed without a vibrant insurance industry, it is very difficult for the economy to grow at the desired levels because of high levels of risk exposure. It also acts as a risk absorber hence investors are assured of their security to their investment (Khrawish & Al-sa'di, 2011). Risk managers help in risk identification, advice in risk prevention measures and cover required. The covers can be placed by intermediaries or direct. When loss has occurred investigators, assessors, loss adjusters, surveyors and brokers help in claim processing and settlement. All these above are regulated by insurance regulatory authority who are mandated by law to regulate, authorize and supervise their activities to protect consumers (Ibe & Odi, 2019).

Before the Fintech revolution, it could take weeks or even months for applicants to receive approval on insurance policies. That process now typically takes mere hours, if not minutes. This remarkable speed increase is primarily due to mobile apps. Mobile apps enable customers to fill out applications from anywhere using easy-to-understand, user-friendly forms. Before now there is traditionally laborious process of filing an insurance claim but many major insurers now

provide a way for customers to file from an app, often taking a few minutes at most. These services make the process more straightforward for users and help organize necessary information for the insurer.

Again the adoption of technology has implied that insurance companies have to adjust from seller centered perspective to buyer centered as the customers are determining the performance of companies (Brady, 2008). Insurance companies in Nigeria use technology for new product conception, marketing, communication and settling of claims including customer relationship management. Most of the insurance companies also uses electronic registration systems (ERS) to ease registration and insurance of registration certificates to insurance companies and intermediaries to ensure consumers are protected and only professionals are offering requires services.

Studies that explain the relationship between financial technology and marketing in insurance reveal contextual, conceptual and methodological gaps. Bett (2012) examined the adoption of GPS tracking technology in the motor vehicle insurance sector in Nigeria. Result reveals that GPS has positive impact as it reduces incidence of theft however his study didn't cover impact of technology in insurance as a whole but only on motor tracking. Francichini (2015) studied the benefits of business operation management tools in Brazil insurance

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companies. it was concluded that it was the fastest growing segment and it needed improvements in its processes in operation for it to remain competitive in global market. the study covered the performance of operation. However this study did not conclude on the effect of technology use in insurance as a whole and the study being in a developed country whose findings would not match in the local environment. Maragia (2016) studied the adaptation of e-marketing strategies by insurance companies in Kenya. The study centered on technological factors, organizational factors and environmental factors. The findings reported that technology has a positive influence on e-market strategies. To fill the existing gap, therefore the study wants to examine the implications of financial technology on the assets of insurance company in Nigeria.

The broad objective of the study is to examine the implications of financial technology on the assets of insurance company in Nigeria. The followings are the specific objectives of the study; investigate the implications of mobile pay on the assets of the insurance company. Determine the implications of A.T.M. on the assets of insurance company. Measure the implications national electronic transfer on the assets of the insurance company

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Financial Technology

Fintech stands for financial technology and refers to computer software and other technology employed to support banking and financial service delivery (Schüffel, 2016). It is a technology based invention that led to the emergence of new business models, processes, applications and products that have significant influence on the financial market and services (Derfleitner, 2017). It is simply the application of financial technologies in the financial industry to improve financial activities (Schüffel, 2016). Fintech companies comprise both start-ups and established companies that are aiming to replace or at least improve the use of financial services provided by incumbent financial companies. They operate in three segments of the financial market, viz; finance, asset management, and payment.

In the financial segment, Fintech companies provide financing services to individuals and Corporations in a number of ways, including crowd funding and crowd lending. In crowd funding, Fintech facilities consist of face-to-face lending between individuals or companies. In the case of crowd lending, Fintech platforms connect companies that are seeking for capital with investors who are willing to lend directly to businesses. One of the benefits of using this platform is that fundraising can be easily set up online to quickly market products and at the same time obtain feedback relating to the product (Augustine, 2015). In the asset

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management segment, Fintech provides three main services, namely; social trading, robo-advice and personal financial management. Social trading involves a social network in which an investor can see, discuss and copy investment collections of other participants (Liu, 2014). Robo-advice is the application of digital systems to create and manage pools of traded funds and other instruments for the investors. It is algorithm-based and sometimes it makes decisions. The main objective of robo-advice is to minimize human intervention in the management of investments (European Supervisory Authorities (ESA), 2015). Investors are charged fees relative to their investment by the providers of robot-advice services.

The payment segment is the main area where the Fintech functions. Here Fintech offers digital payment options that operate both within and outside conventional banking payments systems. For example, e-wallets allow users to store their payment information in order to enable them make real-time transactions (Roubini and Mihm, 2017). Similarly, mobile payment systems enable mobile phone users to effect payments on their mobile phone (Merritt, 2010). These payment systems allow people to transact without stepping in the banking hall. And finally, by doing so, FinTech creates competition not only among the startups working on the service, but also promote competition among banks. The thrust of this research work is to examine effect

of financial technology (Fintech) on corporate performance of banks in Nigeria has become paramount.

Fintech developments in the insurance industry

Financial technologies or financial innovation innovations are reshaping the provision of financial services, creating new opportunities and posing new challenges for both the insurance industry and financial supervisors. In February 2017, the International Association of Insurance Supervisors (IAIS) published the report FinTech Developments in the Insurance Industry, which describes fintech innovations that are relevant to the insurance industry and presents an overview of their potential impacts on the insurance sector and supervisory approaches (Kombo & Tromp, 2009).

Fintech innovations refer to the variety of emerging technologies and innovative business models that have the potential to transform the insurance business. In the insurance sector, the most relevant innovations according to Liu (2014) are in terms of:

- i. Emerging technologies: digital platforms, the Internet of Things, telemetric, big data, data analytics, comparators, robot advisors, machine learning, artificial intelligence and distributed ledger technology, including blockchain and smart contracts
- ii. Business models: peer-to-peer, usage-based and on-demand insurance

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Technological developments and the changing expectations of customers are the main drivers of innovation in the insurance industry. These innovations are being developed both by incumbent insurance companies and by new technology firms or new companies known as insurtech start-ups (Merritt, 2010).

Potential impact of innovations in the insurance business

Fintech innovations have the potential to deliver a wide range of benefits – in particular, efficiency improvements, cost reductions, improved risk assessment, superior customer experience and greater financial inclusion. However, some of these innovations could also have negative implications for consumers and the financial stability of insurance markets (Mike, 2019).

To identify the potential impact of these innovations, the IAIS considered the following three scenarios to assess the extent to which new technology firms could disrupt the insurance business model (Muhammad, 2012):

Scenario 1: Incumbent insurers successfully maintain their customer relationships and leverage technology firms to their own advantage.

Scenario 2: The insurance value chain becomes fragmented as new technology-enabled players enter the market. The traditional customer relationship weakens.

Scenario 3: Incumbent and traditional insurers are completely overtaken by “big tech”

companies – such as Google, Amazon, Facebook or Apple – that provide insurance to fulfill emerging consumer needs.

Automated Teller Machine

Automated teller machine is a specialized computer that makes it convenient to manage a bank account holder's funds. Hannig, & Jansen (2010) sees automated teller machine as a machine that allows a person to check account balances, withdraw or deposit money, print a statement of account activities or transactions, and even purchase stamps. Baber,(2020) stated that an automated teller machine (ATM) is an electronic banking outlet that allows customers to complete basic transactions without the aid of a branch representative or teller. Anyone with a credit card or debit card can access cash at most ATMs, either in the Nigeria or abroad. ATMs are convenient, allowing consumers to perform quick self-service transactions such as deposits, cash withdrawals, bill payments, and transfers between accounts. David-West, Iheanachor, & Kelikume, (2018) sees fees are commonly charged for cash withdrawals by the bank where the account is located, by the operator of the ATM, or by both. Some or all of these fees can be avoided by using an ATM operated directly by the bank that holds the account.

Point of sales services

European Investment Bank. (2014) defines a point of sale (POS) is a place where a customer executes the payment for goods or services and

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where sales taxes may become payable. A POS transaction may occur in person or online, with receipts generated either in print or electronically. The point of sale or point of purchase is the time and place where a retail transaction is completed. At the point of sale, the merchant calculates the amount owed by the customer, indicates that amount, may prepare an invoice for the customer, and indicates the options for the customer to make payment. Hannig, & Jansen (2010) sees a POS System is the overall hardware and software system used for billing in a POS Store. It usually consists of the following units for displaying the order total, product weight, etc. and other hardware units for scanning product barcodes, a printer for receipts and a cash register. A POS (Point of Sale) terminal is a card reading machine or any other device that accepts payments for an order placed on the POS system.

Web transfers services

Dabla-Norris, Yan, & Unsal, (2015) stated that Web file transfer refers to a variety of services that allow users to share files over the web for other people to download. These services are often available for free, though users who want to share very large files may have to pay a fee to do so or for faster file transfers. Web file transfer refers to a variety of services that allow users to share files over the web for other people to download. Mckee, Kaffenberger, & Zimmerman, (2015) opined that these services are often

available for free, though users who want to share very large files may have to pay a fee to do so or for faster file transfers. A number of services offer the ability to transfer files over the web. Glocker, & Piribauer, (2021) opined that POS are marketed to people who want to share large files as email services usually place limits on the size of attachments. Web-based sharing services allow users to share videos and pictures easily. Some of these services include cloud storage such as Drop box or Microsoft One Drive. Muli, (2019). Stated that others are simply websites that offer the ability to upload files for later download. The business model of these services is to offer a free tier with the ability to pay for the ability to upload larger files. Other sites might throttle the download rate for free users and offer faster transfers for paid accounts. Feng, Jingyi, Fang, Tao, Xun, & Zhiyun, C. (2020) stated that all the mobile transfer of money from one bank to another are part of the reason why money are always available in the financial system.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

Theories are formulated to explain, predict, and understand phenomena and, in many cases, to challenge and extend existing knowledge within the limits of critical bounding assumptions. It provides a generalized explanation to an occurrence. The theoretical framework is the structure that can hold or support a theory of a research study (Kombo and Tromp 2009).

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Diffusion of Innovation Theory (1995)

This study is anchored on diffusion of innovation theory, Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory is a popular model used in information systems research to explain user adoption of new technologies. Rogers defines diffusion as ‘the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of a social society (Rogers, 1995). An innovation is an idea or object that is perceived to be new (Rogers, 1995). According to DOI, the rate of diffusion is affected by an innovation’s relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, trialability and observability. (Rogers 1995) defines relative advantage as ‘the degree to which an innovation is seen as being superior to its predecessor’. Complexity, which is comparable to TAM’s perceived ease of use construct, is ‘the degree to which an innovation is seen by the potential adopter as being relatively difficult to use and understand’. Compatibility refers to ‘the degree to which an innovation is seen to be compatible with existing values, beliefs, experiences and needs of adopters’. Trialability is the ‘degree to which an idea can be experimented with on a limited basis’. Finally, observability is the ‘degree to which the results of an innovation are visible’ (Rogers, 1995). The diffusion theory is relevant because it explains the reason why banks adopt technical innovations. One of the reasons why banks adopt technical innovations is relevant advantage. This means that banks that

adopt technical innovations have relatively better financial advantage than those who do not.

Empirical Review

Stephen (2022) examined effect of technology on the performance of insurance industries in Kenya. The study was anchored on the resource dependency theory and the resource-based virw. The descriptive crosssectional survey design was used in the study. The population comprised of all insurance companies in Kenya. There were 54 registered insurance companies in Kenya as at 31st Dec 2021 according to IRA. Data collection was by use of questionnaire which was administered to the marketing manager of each company or equivalent manager who was thought to be a custodian of relevant information relating to the study. Data collected was analyzed and summarized using mean and standard deviation. Further teting was done by use of gression analysis to establish the relationship between technology and performance. the study found out that application of technology leads to enhanced performance whereby document management system is the most widely used technology process. Customer management system, business process management systems and financial management systems were also indicated to be highly used by insurance companies

Bharadwaj, Jack & Suri (2019) carried a research study on financial technology on household resilience to shoks. According to the study,

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developing countries like Kenya are utilizing financial technology tools to build digital loans which can be accessed through mobile phones. the study used both administrative and survey data to investigate the impacts of one of the digital loans in Kenya referred to as M-shwari. From the research findings, digital loans foster household flexibility.

Rodriguez (2019) examined improvement of the financial technology through information systems, computing, communication and connectivity technologies have led to the adoption of the Chatbot technology which in return has improved the performance of the insurance sector in German. This study designated how Chatbot technology has fostered the financial performance of the insurance industry by reducing operational costs, improving insurance efficiency and generating customer trust and loyalty.

Niraula & Kautish (2019) researched on the effect of digitalization and its obstacles in the insurance industry of Nepal. From their research findings, the main challenge is the adoption of the appropriate information technology systems to improve competitiveness, increase profitability, and foster insurance service efficiency. The research study analyzed how policyholders adopted the new technology and the obstacles encountered by the employees in the insurance companies in Nepal. From the study, it was revealed that Nepal Insurance

companies need to do a lot on Fintech to be outstanding in the level of the consumers expectations. Also, several obstacles are hindering the growth of Fintech in the Nepal insurance industry.

Vucec, Spremic & Bach (2017) carried a research study on information technology adoption in the insurance and banking industry with a case study of COBIT usage. According to the study, for any business firm to increase profitability and improve efficiency, embracing information technology should be a priority. A case study of two insurance companies and two commercial banks was undertaken to investigate the implementation of the COBIT (Control Objective for Information and Related Technology) framework in the financial sector. The research emphasizes the importance of strategic information technology used to improve the financial performance of the banking and insurance sectors

Komal,(2009) studied the impact of ATM transactions and cashless payment on cash demand in Austria. In order to assess this effect of ATMs on money demand; the demand for cash was determined by the frequency of withdrawals and by the amount withdrawn. He found out that 94 percent of debit card holders use ATMs to draw cash, while only some 58% of Austrians regularly draw cash at bank counters. Moreover, 14% of respondents regularly acquire cash from other sources. A detailed analysis of the total

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amount withdrawn indicates that about 53% of total cash withdrawn comes from ATMs, it could be inferred that ATM transactions and cashless payments affect optimal cash holdings in two ways.

Jegade (2014) investigates the effects of ATM on the performance of Nigerian banks using responses from questionnaire from a convenience sample of 125 employees of five selected banks in Lagos State with Interswitch network. The results indicate that less than the benefits, the deployment of ATMs terminals have averagely improved the performance of Nigerian banks because of the alarming rate of ATM fraud. He concludes that banks should strive to increase their security layers to subvert the tricks of web scammers.

Okoro (2014) examine the impact of automated teller machine (ATM), point of sales (PoS), Mobile and Internet service values on the intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy using multiple regression technique on time series data of 2006 – 2011. The study reports the following findings: that there is significant relationship between ATM, PoS, Internet service values and the intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy. However, the study also reveals that there is no significant relationship between Mobile service value and intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy within the period under study. He concludes that the ATM, PoS and Internet

services are the major instruments used by the customers of the deposit money banks in Nigeria, and recommends that the banks should put more effort in advertising these products in Nigeria.

Ebiringa (2010) investigated on the effects of ATM infrastructure on the success of e-payment. The study is motivated by the apparent low level of satisfaction with the level of the e-payment services irrespective of the increased deployment of ATM by banks and the need to isolate the critical factors responsible for this. The study was principally based on primary data collected from users of the ATMs and a total of one thousand, one hundred and forty-one (1,141) users of ATM were sampled. The study used weighted scores of the responses to success factors identified in the literature that were analysed using the Factor analysis simulation model. The study concluded that the provision of adequate infrastructure such as power is critical for effective integration of the Nigerian banking system to the global network of electronic payment via ATMs.

Akhisar, Tunay and Tunay (2015) researched the impacts of the bank's productivity execution of electronic-based managing an account administrations in 23 created and building up nations' electronic keeping money administrations through 2005 utilizing dynamic board information techniques. The discoveries of the study set up that bank productivity of created and creating nations was influenced by the proportion of the quantity of branches to the

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quantity of ATMs and were profoundly critical and electronic managing an account administrations in huge. The concentrate likewise found that a few variables had a negative relationship, due to differing qualities in the level of advancement of the nations, the socio-social structure and electronic managing an account base.

Monyoncho (2015) inspected the relationship between E-Banking advances and money related execution of business banks in Kenya utilizing optional information for a time of five years. The discoveries of the study uncovered that ATM developments, Mastercards, portable managing an account and web keeping money offer the comfort of directing a large portion of the saving money exchanges at the time that suits the client. The study presumed that selection of E-Banking advances affected the execution of business banks in Kenya and prescribed that business banks ought to keep putting resources into saving money innovations.

Ogunmuyiwa and Ekone (2010) investigate the impact of money supply on economic growth in

Nigeria between 1980 and 2006, by applying econometric technique OLS, causality test and ECM for time series data, the results reveal that although money supply is positively related to growth but the result is however insignificant in the case of GDP growth rates on the choice between contractionary and expansionary money supply

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Research design is the structure and strategy for investigating the relationship between the variables of the study. The research was adopted to examine effect of financial technology (Fintech) on the corporate performance of banks in Nigeria . The study made use of *ex-post facto* research design. According to Kerlinger and Rint (2006) in the context of social science research an *ex-post facto* investigation seeks to reveal possible relationships by observing an existing condition or state of affairs and searching back in time for plausible contributing factors.

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Model Specification

Ordinary least square regression model was used in the analysis.

The below stated model was used for this study

$$AIC = \beta_0 + \beta_1ATM_t + \beta_2MPAY_t + \beta_3NEFT_t + \mu_t$$

Where:

AIC = Assets of insurance companies.

ATM = Values of automated teller machine

MPAY = Mobile pay

NEFT = National Electronic Funds Transfer

β_0 to β_3 = coefficient of the variables

μ = error term

Definition of Variables

S/N	Type	Variable	Measure/Proxy
1	Independent	Financial Technology	values of ATM and debit card
2	Independent	Financial Technology	Mobile pay
3	Independent	Financial Technology	National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT)
4	Dependent	Insurance Business	Insurance Assets

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

The empirical data are presented in a table which shows the values of proxies; ATM, MPAY and NEFT, 2009 - 2024 are presented in the table below:

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Table 4.1: shows the independent variable, Automated Teller Machine (ATM), values of Mobile Pay, values of National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) for insurance industry in Nigeria; 2009 – 2022.

YEAR	AIC	ATM	MPAY	NEFT
2009	28,934.93	548.6	1.27	13,660.03
2010	37,928.18	399.71	6.65	14,307.32
2011	41,451.22	1,561.74	18.98	14,616.58
2012	50,131.65	1,984.66	31.51	13,087.09
2013	61,600.00	2,828.94	142.8	14,584.80
2014	78,060.48	3,679.88	346.47	14,946.46
2015	85,255.73	3,970.25	442.35	11,030.96
2016	124,267.37	4,988.13	756.9	3,869.85
2017	141,222.03	6,437.59	1,102.00	3,579.12
2018	203,113.12	6,480.09	1,830.70	3,581.99
2019	307,542.61	6,512.61	4,371.55	1,155.64
2020	427,497.16	12,004,067	9,428,512	172,541,642
2021	573,154.46	4.82	244.16	4.47
2022	573,154.46	4.82	244.16	4.47
2023	573,154.46	4.82	244.16	4.47
2024	573,154.46	4.82	244.16	4.47

Source: *NDIC annual report and CBN statistical bulletin from 2009 – 2022*

AIC = Assets of insurance companies.

ATM = Values of automated teller machine

MPAY = Mobile pay

NEFT = National Electronic Funds Transfer

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LOG TRANSFORMED VARIABLES

	LNAIC	LNATM	LNMPAY	LNNEFT
2009	10.2728	6.3073	0.2390	9.5226
2010	10.5434	5.9907	1.8946	9.5685
2011	10.6322	7.3535	2.9433	9.5899
2012	10.8224	7.5932	3.4503	9.4793
2013	11.0284	7.9476	4.9614	9.5877
2014	11.2652	8.2106	5.8477	9.6122
2015	11.3534	8.2865	6.0921	9.3084
2016	11.7301	8.5148	6.6292	8.2609
2017	11.8580	8.7699	7.0048	8.1828
2018	12.2215	8.7764	7.5124	8.1836
2019	12.6363	8.7814	8.3828	7.0524
2020	12.9657	16.3007	16.0592	18.9661
2021	13.2589	1.57327	5.4978	1.49737
2022	13.2589	1.57327	5.4978	1.49737
2023	13.2589	1.57327	5.4978	1.49737
2024	13.2589	1.57327	5.4978	1.49737

Source: *NDIC annual report and CBN statistical bulletin from 2009 – 2022*

LNAIC = Log of Assets of insurance companies.

LNATM = Log of Values of automated teller machine

LNMPAY = Log of Mobile pay

LNNEFT = Log of National Electronic Funds Transfer

UNIT ROOT TEST FOR STATIONARY

In an attempt to confirm the order of integration of the series under study thereby confirming their suitability for a linear combination in the

form of a model, the unit root test following the form specified as Philip and Peron Test was used. Table 4.3 below represents a summary of the unit root result that was stationary.

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Table 4.2: SUMMARY OF UNIT ROOTS TEST RESULTS

Variable	PP Statistic	Critical Values @ 5%	Probability Value	Inference
LNAIC	-6.3222	-3.5484	0.0000	I(1)
LNATM	-4.5527	-3.5485	0.0048	I(1)
LNMPAY	-3.88576	-3.5443	0.0000	I(1)
LNNEFT	-7.0344	-3.5415	0.0000	I(1)

source: Author's e-view 10 output with data in Appendix One.

From the result of Philip and Peron unit root test contained in table 4.2, Log of assets of insurance companies, log of automated teller machine, Log of Mpay and Log of NEFT are all integrated of order 1(1). the Ordinary Least Square Regression Method was used in preference for the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model which tolerates such stationary property combination. In addition the sample size is also good enough for the ARDL given that its estimates remain robust and consistent in the face of not too large sample size and finally good for data

characterized with structural breaks. Also, the variable of LNAIC was log transformed to bring down the data size and ensure linearity.

4.2.2 Basic Descriptive Statistics/ Standard tests for Normality

The statistical properties of the data sets are seen as vital determinants of their behaviors when used in econometric analyses. On the basis of this, the researcher presented in this section, the basic descriptive statistics called Normality test of the variables under study.

Table 4.3: Basic Descriptive Statistics/ Standard tests for Normality:

Description	LNAIC	LNATM	LNMPAY	LNNEFT
Mean	8.693524	6.419931	6.724778	2.144606
Median	8.921368	6.456699	6.962203	2.188245
Maximum	11.75793	10.02224	10.12981	3.146305
Minimum	4.975561	2.148268	2.672078	1.205971
Std. Dev.	2.381641	2.761044	2.609916	0.392521
Skewness	-0.247602	-0.092216	-0.165134	-0.156936
Kurtosis	1.611438	1.576745	1.580685	3.366531
Jarque-Bera	3.622219	3.432784	3.539219	3.388102
Probability	0.163473	0.179713	0.170399	0.823616
Sum	347.7410	256.7973	268.9911	85.78425
Sum Sq. Dev.	221.2164	297.3111	265.6548	6.008843
Observations	12	12	12	12

Source: Author's e-view 10 output with data in Appendix One.

Table 4.3 contains the basic measures of central tendency, spread and variations calculated on the different series of the dataset. All the variables are negatively skewed to the left showing the degree of their departure to the line of symmetry. Also, the Kurtosis of the distribution is less than 3 meaning that they are leptokurtic and are not peaked. Of particular interest is the Jacque-Bera (JB) statistics which is a test for normality. It is a combined test of Skewness (S) of zero (o) and a kurtosis (K) of

three (3), which are signs of a Mesokurtic distribution. In this case, however, the JB statistics shows that the variables are tending to 3 which are signs of Mesokurtic. The assumption of normality is accepted by the JB statistics, as well as the (K) and (S) figures. This, however, does not affect the goodness of the data for the estimation in this study as the kurtosis of all the variables are between 2 and 3 and the Skewness above 0-1 which is consistent with the properties of most financial time series.

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REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Dependent Variable: LNAIC

Method: Least Squares

Date: 02/27/25 Time: 13:05

Sample: 2009 2024

Included observations: 13

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	11.69469	0.162078	72.15475	0.0000
LNATM	0.185575	0.068994	-2.689730	0.0248
LNMPAY	0.344518	0.029362	11.73354	0.0000
LNNEFT	0.370934	0.044336	-1.599918	0.1441
R-squared	0.967220	Mean dependent var	11.58375	
Adjusted R-squared	0.956293	S.D. dependent var	2	0.96073
S.E. of regression	0.200852	Akaike info criterion	0.124833	0.04899
Sum squared resid	0.363075	Schwarz criterion	7	
Log likelihood	4.811417	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.160563	
F-statistic	88.51886	Durbin-Watson stat	2.714473	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			

Based on the above, the interpretation of the results as regard the coefficient of various repressors' is stated as follows:

The value of the intercept which is 0.185 shows that asset of insurance companies in Nigeria will experience 18% increase when all other variables

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are held constant. The estimate coefficients - 0.185(LATM) shows that a unit changes in Values of ATM and debit card will cause 18% increase in asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. The estimate coefficients 0.34(LMPAY) shows that a unit change in Mobile pay will cause 34 % increase in asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. The estimate coefficients 0.7 (LNEFT) shows that a unit changes in National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) will cause 37% decrease in on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria.

From the above table the coefficient of multiple determinations also called R^2 has a value of 0.96 which is also 96% change in dependent variable impacted by independent variable. This 96% shows that the model has a moderate goodness of fit. This also shows that all the variables shows an moderate outcome on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria.

From the same table the F-Statistics shows that all the variables were statistically significant which was represented by (0.0001) with p-value of 0.0001 which is less than 5% margin of significance. Values of ATM has no positive and significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria.

5.0 RESULTS

This study examined the implications of financial technology on the assets of insurance company in Nigeria, using annual time series data from 2009 – 2022. From the analysis carried out, the following findings were postulated:

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) had Positive and non-significant impact on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. Mobile pay had no positive and non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) had negative and non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria.

Conclusion

From the empirical result, it shows that financial technology proxies which include Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Mobile Pay and National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) has non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. From the findings, Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has negative and non-significant effect on return on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria. Mobile pay has no positive and non-significant effect on return on asset of commercial banks in Nigeria National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) has positive and non-significant effect on asset of insurance industry in Nigeria.

Therefore the study concludes that financial technology (Fintech) had positive and non-significant impact on the assets of insurance industry in Nigeria within the period under review.

Recommendations

From the above findings the following recommendation were made:

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There should be a careful study of the system to determine the number of ATM terminals that will ensure its smooth running in Nigeria so as to prevent unnecessary friction in the system. Fair competition should be allowed in order to prevent monopoly-like behavior by the licensed POS manufacturers. The study recommends that insurance industry should consider coming with a clear and fair mobile banking prices which create a universal platform for all banking institutions. This will enhance fair market completion and thus bar financial institutions from customer exploitation. The study also recommends that the financial institutions should continue offering low transaction rates within their Mobile networks and ensure deposits of the various customers are protected at all times.

The services of National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) should be improved as NEFT fund transfer often fail due to some technical glitch that often happen at the time of a heavy load of payments. The charges on National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) services should equally be reduced

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